

Prunum boreale (A. E. Verrill, 1884) is changed to P. borealis

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Prunum boreale (A. E. Verrill, 1884) was made available as *Marginella borealis*, A. E. Verrill 1884. *Borealis* is only an adjective in Classical Latin, but it was substantivized as a noun in Medieval Latin, according to the [Mittellateinisches Wörterbuch](#). The ICZN notes in the [Glossary](#) that Latin “includes both ancient and mediaeval Latin”. Verrill did not make any statement indicating that *borealis* was to be considered as an adjective or a noun, nor that it was derived from a non-Latin or non-Greek word. According to ICZN 31.2.2, the species name must be considered as a noun in apposition to the genus, and the original spelling is to be retained.

Prunum borealis (A. E. Verrill, 1884) is the correct name.

Links:

- [Wikipedia](#)
- [WoRMS](#)

References

- Verrill A. E. (1884). Second catalogue of mollusca recently added to the fauna of the New England Coast and the adjacent parts of the Atlantic, consisting mostly of deep sea species, with notes on others previously recorded. Transactions of the Connecticut Academy of Arts and Sciences, 6(1): 139-294, pl. 28-32, available online at <http://biodiversitylibrary.org/page/7477234>

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